

Proposal and Comparative Analysis of a Voting-Based Election Algorithm for Managing Service Replication in MANETs

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Abstract

Novel approaches are needed to better facilitate dynamic service replication management in mobile ad-hoc networks (MANETs) and to use and apply them within current and emerging autonomous intelligent systems and the Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm. Such approaches should address the *context-awareness* and *self-adaptation* of service replication, while paying special attention to quality attributes (e.g. availability, reliability, etc.) under specific runtime changes and adverse conditions with unstable communications and network partitions. The dynamic election for a node to host a service replica in MANETs can be based on the use of leader election (LE) algorithms. In this research work, a new voting-based election algorithm for managing dynamic service replication in MANETs (namely, VOELA) is proposed. This algorithm is based upon a utility function to score node resources and features (i.e., battery level and topology position) to decide where the service replica will be activated. VOELA is compared to a previously proposed consensus-based algorithm and three other well-known leader election algorithms in terms of service availability, election algorithm reliability, coordination message usage, and network lifetime. For this comparative analysis, the ns-3 network simulator is used together with three different mobility models, namely Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM). The VOELA algorithm demonstrates in balance the most promising results.

Keywords: Leader election (LE), election algorithm, availability, reliability, MANETs, network lifetime

1 Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) paradigm and autonomous intelligent systems are claimed to

provide technological computer-based solutions to interconnect a plethora of emerging, heterogeneous, and smart objects such as wearable/mobile devices with built-in sensors, wheelchairs, robots,

etc., thus creating large and dynamic networks. The number of devices connected to the internet increases every year and is expected to reach 75.44 billion by 2025 [1, 38, 48]. The IoT and autonomous intelligent systems have become a driving force for the development of smart cities and support many other application domains (e.g., healthcare, environmental monitoring, vehicles, transportation, smart homes, tourism, smart retail, agriculture, industry and energy) [1, 38].

Currently, the mobile ad-hoc network (MANET) and wireless sensor network (WSN) constitute a mature communication technologies that are being used as network infrastructure in IoT and its applications [31] to create new MANET-IoT systems [6]. For instance, advanced intelligent transportation systems (ITS) can benefit from these technologies due to factors, such as high mobility and many-to-many communication under collaborative groups [14, 27]. In this kind of scenario, the network topology is constantly and unpredictably changing (i.e., mobility, low battery levels, network partitions or unstable connections), which affects the quality attributes of the deployed services [13]. For this reason, reacting to contextual changes at runtime through self-*/self-star methods (e.g., self-configuration, self-healing, self-optimization or self-protection) becomes a requirement for systems in this context [2, 3, 9, 28, 34, 46].

Replication techniques can improve computer-based resource and service accessibility, reliability, fault-tolerance, and performance. Thus, service replication is applied to prevent data loss when network partitions occur, thereby reducing the number of hops [32, 37, 39, 40, 50]. Moreover, hibernation approaches are of particular interest when demand fluctuates. This is because they reduce response time by activating/hibernating specific services or their replicas on the nodes when needed rather than transmitting them [43].

In this context, deciding when to replicate and where to deploy the new replica are two important issues related to the Leader Election (LE) problem. To solve this problem correctly, three requirements must be addressed: *liveness* or *termination*, which requires performing a finite number of steps for the solution; *uniqueness* or *safety*, which requires that only one processor be elected as a leader; and *agreement*, which requires that all processors know the identity of the elected

leader [4, 21, 41]. The LE is of course applicable to other problems such as the election of superpeers or cluster heads [35].

Several proposals have focused on minimizing the message exchanges and the number of steps that the algorithm needs to perform the election. This reduces the cost of the algorithm in terms of processing time, energy consumption and bandwidth [4, 24, 47].

Additionally, numerous efforts continue to be undertaken to provide better solutions based on the following: (1) availability measurement, i.e., read and relocation cost, data accessibility, and traffic; (2) time needed for network change detection and starting a leader election to deploy a new replica; (3) completion time, that is, the time elapsed between a request being made and complete response being obtained; (4) performance including: average service response time and resource utilization, number of nodes that can access a given service and the number of successful service requests, the time needed to elect k -leaders (where k is the number of leaders that should exist in a group); and (5) election-rate, considering the average number of elections performed by a node per unit of time [10, 21, 33, 47].

The lack of distributed election algorithms designed to operate in highly dynamic environments is the motivation for proposing, as part of previous work, the algorithm presented in [19]. This is referred to here as Consensus, which is a distributed LE algorithm based on an approach where an agreement or consensus is reached to elect the most suitable node or leader to perform a task. It was proven that service replication combined with self-configuration techniques can improve availability, and reliability and minimize power consumption. However, it has been detected that the Consensus algorithm could lead to redundant elections in unreliable network communications due to the loss of messages, which directly affects reliability [20]. In addition, redundant elections may occur because concurrent elections are initiated within the same group of nodes. Both situations lead to more than one leader being elected within a group, unintentionally contravening the uniqueness requirement. Consequently, a new Voting-based election algorithm (called VOELA) is proposed in this paper. Its aim is to improve the election reliability in terms of reducing the number of redundant server elections.

In addition, a comparative analysis is made between VOELA, Consensus, and the other three well-known LE algorithms: Bully [16], Kordafshari [25] and Vasudevan [45]. To facilitate cross comparison, all these algorithms have been implemented and evaluated using the ns-3 simulator¹, under three reference mobility models: Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM) [44], Random Walk Mobility (RWM) [8], and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) [22]. The availability, reliability, use of coordination messages and network lifetime results of each algorithm and each mobility model are compared. VOELA presents a more balanced behavior. It obtains good results in availability and the best results together with Vasudevan in reliability (i.e., minimizing the number of redundant server elections). Additionally, VOELA uses few coordination messages compared to the other algorithms, and it achieves good results in extending the network lifetime.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents a review of the prior research that address relevant issues related to service/resource replication and deployment within mobile and dynamic networks. Section 3 introduces a scoring mechanism approach based on a utility function for LE. Section 4 describes the new VOELA algorithm. Section 5 explains the configuration parameters of the evaluation performed using the ns-3 simulator. Section 6 includes the results and discussion of the comparative analysis between VOELA with Consensus and the other three reference algorithms in terms of service availability, algorithm reliability, coordination message usage and network lifetime. Finally, Section 7 summarizes some conclusions and outlines plans for future research.

2 Related Work

A plethora of proposals have been studied and summarized in this section, which presents LE algorithms, replication methods or both for preserving different quality attributes (e.g., availability, safety, energy, performance, etc.). Most of the proposals include several election criteria for leader/node elections or where to replicate the services. Table 1 summarizes the main characteristics that each proposal exhibits: speeding up

the election (e.g., reducing the number of potential candidates, reducing the message exchanges, etc.), thereby making the process more efficient; the leader or service availability (e.g., either from the time a node remains as a leader or the service is operating); energy efficiency (i.e., one goal of the proposal is to minimize energy consumption); the performance based on several metrics and depending on whether it is over a LE, replication or data access; whether the proposal considers reliable or unreliable network communication; fault tolerance; asynchronous or synchronous system type; specifically whether it considers scenarios with mobile nodes; and in relation to the evaluation, whether it has been tested using a simulator or tool.

Bully [16] is a classic algorithm used as a reference for subsequent proposals. Nodes have an identifier (from 1 to n , where n is the number of nodes in the network) that indicates the priority and the one with the highest priority is chosen as the leader. However, it assumes that the system is synchronous, each node has a unique ID, the node IDs are known, the nodes do not pause, and that the algorithm is fault-tolerant but it has safe cells that survive failure. The number of messages that are exchanged with Bully depends on the ID of the node that starts the LE, and the cost is higher if the process is started by the node with the lower ID. Additionally, another algorithm is presented in [16], the Invitation algorithm which is an asynchronous alternative to the Bully algorithm where some of the previous assumptions are relaxed (i.e., communication failures and node pauses may occur). Therefore, messages, received from external groups, that are related to the election can be ignored. Group coordinators, using a priority mechanism, periodically send invitations to other groups, asking them if they want to join the group they coordinate. Here, nodes that belong to a group share a unique group number. The authors believe that this approach can be used in unreliable environments but there is no evidence.

The election criteria differ for LE, but most approaches use a utility function. An improvement on the algorithms Secure Extrema Finding Algorithm (SEFA) and Secure Preference-based Leader Election Algorithm (SPLEA) based on spanning tree is presented in [45]. The election is based on the node value calculated from the

¹<https://www.nsnam.org/>

Table 1: Overview of the proposals examined related to LE algorithms and replication mechanisms. (-) Not specified or stated; (✗) Not implemented; (✓) Implemented.

Year	Reference	LE algorithm	Replication method	Election/Replication criteria	Availability	Energy	Reliability/Safety	Network traffic	Unreliable network communication	Node/Service failure tolerant	Asynchronous system type	Mobile network type	Evaluation	Mobility model
1982	[16]	Bully Invitation	-	Highest ID	-	-	-	-	✗	✗	✗	✗	-	-
				Highest Group ID	-	-	-	-	✗	✗	✗	✗	-	-
2004	[45]	SEFA and SPLEA	-	Utility function (battery life or computational capabilities)	✓	-	-	-	✓	✗	✓	✓	GloMoSim	RWP
2014	[33]	K-leader election algorithm	-	Higher energy or computational capabilities	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓	✓	Testbed with MicaZ motes	RWP
2017	Proposed [19]	Consensus	✓	Utility function (network topology and energy level)	✓	-	-	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	ns-3	RWM
2018	[41]	DELFA	-	Utility function (residual battery, computing power, memory, node degree, mobility and hop distance between nodes)	✓	-	✓	✓	✗	✓	-	✓	✓	-
	[5]	-	✓	Utility function with highest resource strength from available resources (CPU, memory capacity, and residual energy)	✓	✓	-	-	-	✓	-	✗	No simulator used but a few devices connected	-
2019	[10]	-	✓	CPU cycle, energy, memory, and available bandwidth	✓	✓	-	✓	-	-	-	✗	Java Agent Development Framework	No
2020	[24]	DoTRo	-	Identifier or capability (i.e., battery, residual energy, network x-coordinate, etc.) using LMF	-	✓	-	✓	-	✓	-	✗	CupCarbon	-
	[4]	FRLLE	-	Leader coefficient concept (minimum failure rate, minimum average load, average CPU, memory and bandwidth usage)	✓	-	✓	✓	✗	✓	✗	-	GCC version of C language and MPICH version of message passing interface (MPI)	-
2022	[21]	SEALEA	-	-	✓	✓	-	✓	✗	✓	✓	✗	OMNET++	No
	[42]	NAM-Hub	-	Utility function (RSSI, battery level, and CPU)	-	-	-	✓	-	✓	-	✓	Test with 3 Smartphones (Android) and 3 BLE Beacons	People walking
Current proposal	VOELA	✓	✓	Dynamic utility function (network topology and energy level)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	ns-3	Manhattan Grid, RWM, RPGM

remaining battery or the computational capabilities to guarantee the high availability of a leader. A node starts building a spanning tree in response to the departure of the current leader. However, the reception of a message is assumed if the nodes remain connected during transmission and node failure is not considered. The simulation is carried out with the GloMoSim simulator and node mobility is determined by the Random Waypoint mobility model (RWP). [33] presented a distributed K-leader election labeled Election-Main and an optimized version labeled, Election-Opt. Both algorithms focus on electing the top-K weighted leaders, where the nodes with the higher energy or computational capabilities prevail and are voted as RED nodes while the rest are referred

to as WHITE nodes. The RED nodes build diffusion trees to collect the weights. When the highest weight RED node collects all network information, it elects the K-top leaders and spreads the election results to the network nodes. The algorithm addresses three correctness properties (safety, liveness and agreement); it operates in asynchronous environments and is scalable and fault-tolerant. The performance is evaluated based on four metrics: the fraction of time without K-leaders; the election-rate considering the average number of elections performed by a node per unit time; the election-time from the time in which the node is part of the election process and it gets to know the K-leaders; and the message-overhead defined as the average number of messages that each node transmits within the election process. Simulation

parameters are specified but no details about the simulation tool used are provided. The algorithm is also implemented on a testbed with MicaZ nodes. Another election algorithm based on flooding and spanning trees, namely, Dominating Tree Routing (DoTRo), is presented in [24]. As a first step, several local leaders are elected, using the Local Minima Finding Algorithm (LMF) which follows the Minimum Finding Algorithm (MinFind) principle [36]. With MinFind, each node, at the beginning, assigns its local network value, calculated based on battery, residual energy, network x-coordinate, etc., to its x_{min} variable and will broadcast its score only once across the network. When a node receives a lower score from another node, it updates its x_{min} variable and broadcast the new score across the network. This process is repeated and after a certain time (t_{max}), it is assumed that only one node does not have received a lower score than the one it had; therefore, this is the leader, also called the local leader. DoTRo is composed of an initialization part, a second part where LMF is launched, and as a third part, the flooding process. When two trees meet, the tree with the lowest value prevails. The evaluation is carried out with the CupCarbon simulator and analyzes the number of messages sent and received, the energy consumption, and the duration of the election process.

A wider set of criteria are being considered within the DEMocratic Leader Finding Algorithm (DELFA) [41] which has been proposed as an improvement of the Message Efficient Leader Finding Algorithm (MELFA) and Elite Leader Finding Algorithm (ELFA). DELFA satisfies safety and liveness properties and is structured in three phases. The algorithm can only be initiated by nodes whose weight is greater than 69 (initiation or phase 1) and that the nodes must have at least a minimum battery to prevent the leader from failing in a short period of time. Within the reception of concurrent election messages or phase 2, DELFA creates a group, namely, the house, which is composed of a limited number of the best nodes (i.e., nodes with the best capabilities or weights). It also elects the three best nodes, which are the president node, the leader node, and the vice-leader node, according to their capabilities (i.e., remaining battery, computing power, memory, mobility, node degree, and hop distance

between nodes). When the current leader and the vice-leader nodes are unavailable (e.g., during re-election), the president becomes the leader. Phase 3 is composed of the announcement of the leader from among the home nodes, but then the leader keeps sending heartbeat messages. It is assumed that nodes have enough storage capacity to store messages and that the communication links are bidirectional and reliable. A theoretical evaluation and a simulation have been carried out. However, no details of the simulator used or of the mobility models have been provided. In [5], an election algorithm is proposed where the leader will be the node with higher resources (CPU capacity, memory and residual energy). When the leader node fails the election process starts within the unidirectional ring network. The process includes the formation of the Resource Strength Status Queue array, sorted in descending order by scores (i.e., the node with the highest score is positioned at the top of the queue). Each node sends its score to its successor, and this one adds its own score to the list and shares it again with the next node. It is considered that a node that has been disconnected can be reconnected after some time and that a new node can be added to the network, but it is assumed that those would be initialized with the current leader's information. The evaluation is performed with computers that form a 6-node network. The failure rate and the load-based leader election (FRLLE) algorithm is presented in [4]. The leader coefficient concept is also introduced, which involves the minimum failure rate, minimum average load, average CPU, memory and bandwidth use. The nodes are connected by a bidirectional synchronous ring. The proposal follows a 3-stage structure for choosing the leader with low failure and loading rates and more reliability. If a node fails, the objective is to restore it to an error-free state. The election process involves three messages. First, the election message contains the leader coefficient. Second, the leader recovery message contains the failed leader identifier. The third message contains the identifier of the new elected leader. The global information of the system is not necessary to elect a leader, but the leader coordinates the communications and tasks of the system. If the leader fails, the algorithm checks if it has recovered before electing a new leader. If there is no recovery, the algorithm

elects the node with the minimum leader coefficient. In the proposal, it is intended to ensure that there is one leader (liveness) but not more than one at the same time (safety), as well as minimizing the message exchanges and taking fewer steps to determine the leader. The evaluation was carried out on a computer with the GCC version of the C language and the MPICH version of the message passing interface (MPI). The simulation has been focusing on addressing the problem of data inconsistency because of servers replication. The number of exchanged messages and time metrics were measured.

In [10], a proactive service replication scheme was presented for a smart-city IoT scenario based on a context awareness with the aim of improving service availability, service response-time and system width. The set of potential servers to host the replicas has to be determined. The nodes possess two vectors, one for resources (i.e., remaining CPU cycle, energy, memory, and available bandwidth) and another to specify the weights to be assigned to resources, from which the utility of each agent will be calculated. The scheme includes service identification that will need to be replicated in the immediate future and an optimal multiagent task for batch decision-making. An emulation is carried out in the Java Agent Development Framework, and performance is evaluated in terms of average service response time, resource utilization and service drop rate.

Another 5-phase asynchronous LE was proposed in [21] called the scalable and energy-Aware leader election algorithm (SEALEA). The election begins with nodes called initiators, which are selected by receiving the highest number of votes in response to broadcasting their weight. Then, initiators create an election message that is sent to RecNodes and contains information from the sender. Each sender is considered the parent of the receiver obtaining a list of recipients. Receivers send a response (i.e., delete to indicate if the node has already received an election message from the same node, which is not found to indicate that its weight and that of its children is less than the one it has received, or found to contain the list of nodes that have a higher weight than the one received). When all responses are received, a winning message is sent. A simulation is performed with OMNET++ with a nonmobile network of nonvariable size, and

communication is assumed to be error-free. The metrics of messages exchanged, data transmitted and energy remaining are evaluated. In [42], M-Hub with Neighborhood Awareness (NAM-Hub) was a leader election mechanism proposed to elect the most suitable leader, and the subleader would act as a mobile gateway at the edge for other smart objects discovered opportunistically. The subleader is a candidate to become a leader when the leader is no longer accessible. NAM-HUB is within M-Hub middleware that collects and processes data from other devices. Once the election process starts, a message is sent with the list of objects without a leader, and M-HUB calculates the scores of the list of objects received and returns them to the node that started the process. Scores are calculated with a utility function (i.e., an equation with different weights for RSSI, battery level, and CPU). If the M-Hub does not know the nodes in the list, then the message is ignored. The election is finalized when there is consensus. A test in a real environment was performed with 3 smartphones and 3 BLE beacons. Observed message transmission, message exchange times, disconnections, and analyzed failure detection and leader recovery times.

Researchers are approaching and providing solutions to this problem from different perspectives. Some examples of theoretical approaches are as follows. In [26], it was defined as the specification of a leader service for dynamic systems and a leader election algorithm that solves the problem considering some synchronous assumptions. External time, system dynamicity, the dynamic system model and property statements are formally denoted. This work is extended in [18], and the proposed model includes some additional properties for an asynchronous LE where there are mobile processes within dynamic distributed systems. The network is defined as a graph where the nodes are the vertices and the edges are bidirectional links of the nodes. It defines the need for a stable connection (*direct connectivity*) for a period of time to perform the transmission. They introduce s , as a way of considering periods where there is a limit but priority is unknown and bad periods where there is no limit. Moreover, timeliness, process or channel failures, partitions, diameter and stability of graphs, and number of processes in any graph are defined as dimensions. In addition,

authors define connectivity and election properties, and redefine two of which define the Dynamic Omega failure detector class.

In [12], a self-stabilizing and silent asynchronous distributed algorithm (SSLE) was presented for bidirectional networks where the processes have unique IDs. Three algorithms are presented, with Algorithm III being the most complete version. Each process has several variables (i.e., ID, leader, key, level, parent) and a number of actions (i.e., join, reset, color 1, color 2, and update done). In addition, functions (i.e., self_Key(P), Succ_Key(P), Best_Nbr_Key(P), etc.) are defined with guards and statements. Each node has its own ID, an ID of the node that is its leader, and the distance that separates them. It was detected that Algorithm II did not self-stabilize if there was a fictitious leader whose ID was less than the ID of the leader. This issue was solved in Algorithm III, including an upper bound that does not allow the process level to exceed the diameter. It will be elected as the leader of the process with the lowest ID. Additionally, a process P can be attached to a neighboring process Q in the recruitment. Roots, true and false children can be created, and there are components (processes connected to true children) whose processes have the same leader (component leader). In Algorithm III, if a process cannot be joined to a different component, it changes its root to true, although this method is not always effective. Within an informal proof, seven benchmarks are specified, and as the main results, it is determined that SSLE has $O(\log n)$ space complexity bits per node, so it converges within $O(n)$ rounds with an unfair daemon. In $O(diam)$ more rounds, with $diam$ being the diameter of the network, are silent. Furthermore, [30] presented a resilient LE algorithm that integrated building-block operators for spreading information by the network, summarizing information to be used by interacting units, and holding a temporary state. Nodes are identified by unique IDs. The diameter of the network is estimated without prior knowledge of the network. A node is attached to a leader, the closest one. The distance between nodes is estimated from the recursion distance proposed in [29], and each node has the diameter of the subnetwork of nodes sharing the same leader. Nodes can accept a leader of their neighbor if the propagation radius is

higher than the estimated distance. Several leaders could be acceptable and the one with highest priority is elected. However, a leader gives up his status if a neighbor is linked to a higher priority leader within his radius of reach. Resistance is demonstrated mathematically in case there are fake leaders or a legitimate leader is lost (i.e., disturbances). Overestimation of the distance estimate and stabilization are also proven for some cases. The stabilization time is $O(diameter)$.

Nevertheless, not all proposals evaluate availability, network lifetime (energy), reliability and safety or network traffic to compare the impact of their contributions. In most cases, connections are assumed to be reliable, although the potential failures of leaders are increasingly being considered. Not all proposals present asynchronous systems, nor do they incorporate a study considering the growing trend of mobility of the network nodes. Furthermore, our proposal does not require prior knowledge of the network. In addition, the Bully algorithm and its derivatives, such as Kordafshari, base their choice on static IDs. This does not allow these algorithms to be used to elect the best host in a network where conditions change at runtime. Therefore, an update has been made to encode the dynamic ranking parameters in the ID to compare with our proposal, which is presented in Section 5.

3 Utility Function

A utility function is a mechanism for assessing the feasibility of a node hosting a replica of service and acting as a server. There are several features of the context that must be considered for LE. However, depending on the scenario, not all of them would be equally relevant. For this reason, a generic evaluation function is proposed in Subsection 3.1.

Additionally, in highly dynamic networks and MANETs, node conditions and network topology are constantly changing [51]. All the features selected in advance and their weights considered in the evaluation function are not adequate for specific scenarios and situations after a series of changes in the execution context or indeed the objective of the system. The selected evaluation function would therefore be sub-optimal. To resolve this problem, we propose a self-adaptive evaluation function (Subsection 3.2).

3.1 Generic Evaluation Function

A generic Equation 1 of the utility function is proposed with the objective that as many features as needed can be considered in a given scenario.

$$\begin{aligned} score &= w_0 \cdot f_0 + w_1 \cdot f_1 + \dots + w_n \cdot f_n \\ \text{for } w_i, f_i &\in [0, 1], \sum_{i=0}^n w_i = 1 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where:

f_i = normalized value of feature i

w_i = weight assigned to feature i

n = number of features considered

The evaluation function returns a limited value between $[\lambda_{min}, \lambda_{max}]$, where λ_{max} represents the maximum affinity of the node to host an active replica of the service and λ_{min} the minimum. In a desire to provide maximum flexibility and facilitate the system reconfiguration, the utility function returns a weighted average from each element considered for evaluation (i.e., battery, storage, bandwidth, etc.) together with its associated weight, which determines how relevant that element is in the evaluation of a node to host the activated replica. For example, if in a situation the battery level is especially relevant, the weight associated with it should simply be increased and the nodes with the highest battery would be prioritized for selection.

The position of the node in the network topology is a fundamental feature to consider for managing the service replication. The availability, reliability, and performance of distributed applications are critically conditioned by the service placement in the distributed system [7, 49].

Generally, in dynamic networks, routing protocols represent only the best path between nodes according to a given metric (number of hops, bandwidth, reliability, etc.) [7, 49]. Therefore, a routing table (reachable node ID, number of hops and gateway) is maintained at each node. This information can be useful to determine the approximate position of a node within an ad-hoc network. While the location of the node cannot be determined exactly, it can be used to determine whether the node is more centrally located or more peripherally located within the network. For this approach to be viable, it is necessary to keep the

routing table of each node updated reflecting any changes in the ad-hoc network. As a consequence, proactive routing protocols are necessary.

Proper selection and weight adjustment can favor or indeed impair performance (service availability, battery consumption, number of elections, etc.) of the system supported by the adequacy of the LE.

3.2 Self-adaptive Evaluation Function

The status and condition of resources on the network change over time. This can cause system priorities to change as execution progresses. An example of this is the battery level of the nodes. Initially, all nodes usually have a high or, at least, acceptable battery level. Therefore the battery level may not be a determining factor in deciding the host for an active replica. However, when the battery starts to deplete, taking this feature into consideration or increasing its influence can lead to a longer lifetime for many of the nodes in the network.

For this reason, a self-adaptive approach is proposed, which considers several predefined evaluation functions. In this way, the most appropriate evaluation function can be selected at runtime according to the state of the network to improve certain quality attributes of the system (e.g., to extend the lifetime of the nodes). For this purpose, the leader of each group of nodes acts as a monitor, and therefore, receives regular updates on the status of the nodes' characteristics in its group (e.g., the battery level). When a predefined condition is reached, for instance, the average battery level of the group drops below 50%, the leader notifies the other nodes in its group to change their evaluation function, thus apportioning greater priority to the battery.

It should be noted that not all nodes may receive the notification at the same time and that at a certain point different nodes may be using a different evaluation function. However, this does not block or stop the election process, as the score of the nodes will always be a floating value between 0 and 1. Furthermore, in a network with sufficient interactions between nodes and where conditions affect the nodes in a uniform manner (e.g., all nodes are consuming battery power), over

time all nodes in the network will converge to the same evaluation function.

This approach is independent of the election algorithm to the extent that it simply uses a utility function as the election criteria.

4 VOELA LE algorithm

This work introduces a new LE algorithm, entitled the voting-based election algorithm (VOELA), based upon a voting approach. It should be emphasized that while this algorithm has been designed for the election of a host in a highly dynamic ad-hoc network also it can be applied to other scenarios where it is necessary to elect a process or node to act as coordinator.

A node can be in three possible states:

- **Local**, when the node is isolated;
- **Server**, when the node is hosting a replica of a service; and
- **Client**, when the node is not hosting an active replica but has established a satisfactory client-server connection with a node in the **server** state.

Therefore, to determine the node that will host the active replica the LE algorithm is executed in a distributed manner.

There is no difference between a node initiating the election and a node participating in the election because all nodes follow the same procedure. Unlike other proposals, the procedure is not restarted each time a request is received and nor is any distinction made between nodes that started the procedure earlier and those that started it later. This can be seen as concurrent elections, but in fact, the algorithm takes advantage of this to distribute the *Score* messages. Additionally, score messages are used to determine which nodes are available for election. In other words, a node that does not broadcast its score is not eligible to be elected as a host.

The main reasons a node might not broadcast its scores are:

- (1) the node is not available due to a malfunction (hardware or software);
- (2) the node does not have sufficient hardware capabilities to host a service (e.g., it does not have sufficient battery);

- (3) the node is still in the process of calculating its score using the evaluation function, since there may be a delay between individual nodes in the execution of the distributed algorithm.

The objective of VOELA is to provide enhanced robustness against message loss compared to its antecedent Consensus. The VOELA LE algorithm operates on three different kinds of coordination messages:

- The *score* message transmits the score of the node. This score is obtained through a utility function.
- A *voting* message is used by the node to cast a vote to the best-scored node.
- *Elected coordinator* message to proclaim the election victory of a node to the other nodes involved in the process.

The VOELA algorithm starts an election considering the following situations:

- a new node appears within the group;
- the current leader goes offline (e.g., it moves away from the group or turns off the device) or starts running out of resources (e.g., draining its battery); and
- a *score* message is received, which indicates that another node has started an election;

To detect these situations, we propose to use the information that the routing protocol collects in the routing table of the node (i.e., connection between nodes, node neighbors, and paths between nodes), and a monitoring process that detects any changes in the routing table (Subsection 3.1). This requires a proactive routing protocol, such as OLSR [23]. This approach is not particular to the VOELA algorithm and could be replaced by other discovery service implementations. Moreover, depending on the application scenario, some of these conditions may be of greater importance than others or additional situations can be added in the future.

The flow of the election process is depicted below (Figure 1):

- **When a node N starts the election process:**

- (1) N determines its score via an evaluation function.

was started for each of them, the network could become overloaded with coordination messages. Therefore, in order to start the election process only when the network could be considered stable, the start of the process is delayed for a predefined time from the detection of the event. If the network is more stable, the probability of the election being made correctly increases. If new events are detected before the timer expires and a stable connection is not achieved, the timer is restarted and the nodes will remain in the local state. This waiting time can also be used to give the nodes a reaction margin when they are performing other higher priority tasks. To establish this value accurately, empirical tests must be carried out for each specific case; otherwise the value would be an approximation. Moreover, this approach reduces the occurrence of unnecessary election processes, when the network topology has multiple changes in a short period of time. Regarding scalability, if the number of nodes appearing is excessively high (e.g., two large network partitions are merged into one), it could saturate the communication network. In this respect, additional node clustering methods could be used.

Figure 2 depicts a message exchange in a group of three nodes to perform an election. The network consists of Node 1, with a score of 0.9, Node 2, with a score of 0.8, and Node 3, with a score of 0.7. These scores are obtained through the utility function and reflect the suitability of the node to act as a server. The election is initiated by Node 1, which switches to the local state and sends its score to Nodes 2 and 3. These nodes switch to the local state and send their score to the rest of the nodes. Once the nodes have received all the scores, they cast their vote. Since the highest rated node is Node 1, Nodes 2 and 3 send a *vote* message to it. By receiving these votes, in addition to its own vote, Node 1 already has the majority to win the election. For this reason, it switches to server state and sends an *elected coordinator* message announcing its victory to Nodes 2 and 3. These nodes, upon receiving the *elected coordinator* message, switch to the client state, establishing Node 1 as the server.

4.1 Proof of Correctness

This subsection presents the proof of the correctness of the VOELA algorithm, assuming reliable

communication channels, that all nodes have a unique ID and that there are no malicious nodes.

Lemma 1 *Within the same election process, it is not possible for two different nodes to receive $\frac{n}{2} + 1$ votes.*

Proof Let two nodes P and Q participate in the same election process where n nodes are involved. If during the election process P and Q each receive $\frac{n}{2} + 1$ votes, at least $2(\frac{n}{2} + 1) = n + 2$ votes must have been cast. However, this is not possible, given that in the election process each participating node casts only one vote, limiting the total number of votes to n . \square

Lemma 2 *A voting process cannot lead to a tie.*

Proof Suppose there is a group G of n nodes, with $n \in 2\mathbb{N} + 1$. It cannot happen that P and Q each have $\frac{n}{2}$ votes. Either P receives $(\frac{n}{2} + 1)$ and Q receives at most $(\frac{n}{2} - 1)$ votes or vice versa.

With $n \in 2\mathbb{N}$, let us suppose P and Q with scores S_p and S_q , where $S_p = S_q$ and $S_p > S_i, \forall i \in G, i \neq p$ and $i \neq q$. Then, a node U will cast its vote to the node with the lowest ID of P and Q . As IDs are unique, a tie is not possible. \square

Lemma 3 *If two or more nodes in the same group start a concurrent election, only one leader is elected in the group.*

Proof Let two nodes P and $Q \in G$. P and Q start an election independently, at times t_p and t_q respectively. If $|t_p - t_q| \leq t_s$, with t_s being the time that a node waits for more *Score* messages, the nodes will consider the *Score* messages to belong to the same election process. Thus, the concurrent election processes become a single process, and according to Lemmas 1 and 2 only one leader will be elected. In the case that $|t_p - t_q| > t_s$, the election processes are not concurrent but sequential with the most recent election process prevailing. \square

Lemma 4 *The algorithm ends.*

Proof Suppose a network $N = (V, E)$, with a node $P \in N$ and $\text{deg}(P) = 0$, then P remains in the local state. If $\text{deg}(P) > 0$, t_s expires without receiving scores. Then, P remains in the local state without

Fig. 2: Exchange of messages to perform an election with VOELA between three nodes: Node 1 with a score of 0.9, Node 2 with a score of 0.8 and Node 3 with a score of 0.7.

electing a leader. Since it is assumed that there is reliable communication, the absence of scoring messages is due to the reconfiguration of the network topology and a new election process will need to be initiated. If $\deg(P) > 0$, P receives m votes, with $m \in [1, n]$, the election process continues. Then, by Lemmas 1 and 2 one node will be elected as the leader, finalizing the election process. \square

In relation to asynchronous systems, the FLP (Fischer, Lynch, and Paterson) impossibility theorem [15] demonstrates that consensus cannot be guaranteed in this type of system if at least one of the nodes can experience failures. Additionally, the CAP (Consistency, Availability, and Partition Tolerance) theorem [17] shows that in this type of system, where messages may be lost, two of the properties of consistency, availability, and network partition tolerance can be guaranteed, but not all three at the same time. VOELA addresses this by terminating without electing a leader in the case of a transient network partition, providing consistency at the expense of availability.

Lemma 5 *In a group of n nodes, if $\frac{n}{2} + 1$ nodes disconnect and reconnect then no leader is elected.*

Proof Let be a group of n nodes, if $\frac{n}{2} + 1$ nodes disconnect before sending their vote, restart and reconnect, only a maximum of $\frac{n}{2} - 1$ votes will have been cast in a group of n nodes, which prevents the election of a leader. \square

In the context of Lemma 5, a deadlock can be avoided through the use of timers, preventing a

node from waiting indefinitely for the vote of the rest of the nodes. Additionally, this situation can be avoided by triggering a new election when a new node appears (or reconnects), invalidating the previous election.

4.2 Algorithm Message Complexity

A theoretical analysis allows us to verify the behavior of the algorithm in a simplified environment. This is carried out according to the metrics proposed by Coulouris et al. [11]. As stated by these authors, the performance of a distributed election algorithm is measured by (1) the total bandwidth usage, which is translated into the number of messages sent during the election; and (2) the response time, given by the transmission time of serialized messages. In this analysis, the mobility of the nodes is not taken into consideration.

In general, the complexity of an election algorithm can vary according to which node begins the election or according to the network topology in the case of algorithms based on bully approaches or spanning trees. It should be noted that the VOELA algorithm is not affected by these factors and complexity remains constant in reliable environments where there is no loss of coordination messages. This is because the steps in the algorithm are not conditioned by the position of the nodes in the topology or their particular score.

Specifically, the message complexity of the algorithm, with n as the number of nodes involved in the election, is given by:

- $n \cdot (n-1)$ *Score* messages, since, in the first stage of the algorithm, each node broadcasts its score to all nodes except itself.
- $(n-1)$ *Vote* messages, where the n nodes vote for the top ranked node. It should be noted that the top ranked node votes itself, which does not involve sending an actual message, but an internal increment in the vote counter of the node.
- $(n-1)$ *Elected Coordinator* messages, with which the node that has won the election announces its victory to the other nodes.

Consequently, the message complexity is given by $n^2 + n - 2 \in \mathcal{O}(n^2)$. The turnaround time of the election is $3t_{msg}$, where t_{msg} is the time necessary to transmit a message between two nodes because *Score*, *Vote* and *Elected Coordinator* messages must be serialized.

Note that a node can be elected with $\frac{n}{2} + 1$ votes, which would involve $\frac{n}{2}$ *vote* messages, taking into account that the best node votes itself locally. For this reason, if a node receives the *elected coordinator* message before sending its vote, it can cancel the sent *vote* message as it is not necessary. Therefore, in the best case scenario the election can be carried out with $\frac{n}{2}$ *Vote* messages, instead of $(n-1)$, resulting in a message complexity of $n^2 + \frac{n}{2} - 1 \in \mathcal{O}(n^2)$.

To verify the complexity analysis, the VOELA algorithm is applied to a stationary mesh network in ns-3 (Figure 3). Evaluating a stationary network ensures that a single election is performed, facilitating comparison with the complexity analysis performed. The the empirical results obtained remain within the defined theoretical bounds, following a quadratic trend of $0.996n^2 + 0.786n - 1.76$ with an adjustment of $R^2 = 1$.

5 Simulation Configuration

Cross comparison of VOELA performance has been undertaken using version 3.21 of the ns-3 network simulator. The basic configuration of the nodes used is described in Table 2. It should be noted that it is assumed that, unlike in the proof of correctness, the communication channels are not reliable and messages may be lost due to transmission errors, collisions, channel fading, and buffer congestion. As a consequence, the simulated model will be a partially synchronous model,

Fig. 3: Coordination messages used by VOELA to perform an election on stationary mesh networks composed of 15 to 30 nodes.

i.e., no process failures are considered, but there are network partitions, communication channel failures and asynchrony between network nodes.

Table 2: Node setting parameters used in ns-3 to perform the simulations.

Wi-Fi Standard	802.11b
Transportation Protocol	TCP
Data Rate	250 Kbps
Propagation Delay Model	Constant Speed
Propagation Loss Model	Two Ray Ground model: wave length (58.25 mm); system loss (1); minimum distance (0.5 m); height above z (1.5 m)
Routing Protocol	OLSR
Connection Range	250 m
Battery Capacity	2.45 Ah
Initial Charge	[1.0-2.45] Ah

To facilitate the cross-comparison of the performance of the VOELA algorithm, the election algorithms Bully [16], Kordafshari [25] and Vasudevan [45] have been selected.

The Bully algorithm has been selected because it has become one of the most popular election algorithms since it was proposed in 1982. The Kordafshari et al. algorithm is a variant of the Bully algorithm, which was proposed to reduce the number of *coordination messages* and redundant elections. Therefore, Kordafshari does not add new assumptions to the existing ones for the

Bully algorithm. Finally, as seen in Section 2, the Vasudevan proposal distinguished itself as one of the few current approaches that does not assume reliable communication channels.

The Bully algorithm bases the leader election on the ID of the nodes and assumes that the IDs of the nodes are static and known. Thus, the Bully algorithm, in its current form, does not apply to scenarios where the election is based on a score variable in time. This is also the case with the Kordafshari algorithm. Consequently, to overcome this limitation and make it possible to apply the Bully and Kordafshari algorithms in the context of this work, the following minor modifications are introduced, which do not change the essence of these algorithms:

- The coordination messages, *Election* and *Answer*, contain the score information obtained by the sender node using the utility function.
- *Election* messages are only sent to the highest scoring nodes based on the last known score of the nodes.
- *Answer* messages are sent as a reply when the source of the *election* message has a lower score.
- Using the last known scores, a node may receive an *election* message from another node with a higher score. When this happens, the node will wait for the *coordinator* message, because it knows that there is another node with a higher score available on the network.

Additionally, the VOELA algorithm is compared with the previously proposed Consensus election algorithm [19].

The utility function for the simulations will value two characteristics of the nodes in all cases: the battery and its position within the network topology. It is given by the formula shown in Equation 2, where bl refers to the remaining battery level and dcm refers to the normalized direct connections of the node, both in the range $[0, 1]$. The direct connections are given by the number of direct (single-hop) connections of the node, divided by the total number of nodes within the group. Then, using the routing table, we can know how good the node's position within the network topology is.

Empirical tests were carried out to determine the weights. Therefore, $w_1 = 0.6$ and $w_2 = 0.4$ are assigned, giving slightly more relevance to the battery of the node than to its position within

the network. The utility function returns a value between 0 and 1, with 1 being the maximum value a node can obtain.

$$score = w_1 \cdot bl + w_2 \cdot dcm$$

$$\text{for } w_i, bl, dcm \in [0, 1], \sum_{i=0}^n w_i = 1 \quad (2)$$

The five election algorithms have been evaluated under three mobility models: Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), which aims to represent an urban area or an indoor scenario and can be related to ITS (intelligent transportation system) and smart cities application areas; Random Walk Mobility (RWM), which is one of the predominant models because of its simplicity and, although it cannot be considered a realistic scenario, it represents the worst scenario in terms of the dynamicity of the network topology; and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM), which is designed to simulate the behavior of groups in open areas and can be related to emergency scenarios & situations and smart cities application areas. Setup parameters regarding the mobility are shown in Table 3 for each mobility model. The simulated geographical area is one square kilometer and the speed of the nodes is intended to be similar to that of a person on foot. The BonnMotion support tool has been used to generate the traces of Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models, whereas ns-3 provides native support for the Random Walk Mobility (RWM) model. A network where the necessary services are already deployed is assumed. In this way, the proposal activates or hibernates the corresponding replicas (self-configuring) and there are no additional deployment costs at runtime.

The number of nodes comprising the network ranges from 4 to 30. Because no clustering techniques are applied to improve the scalability of the network and there is a high degree of mobility in the scenario, the number of coordination messages generated for networks of 25 to 30 nodes starts to collapse the network, making it difficult for some of the evaluated algorithms to finish the election processes correctly. Each combination of the number of nodes in the network, algorithms and mobility models was simulated 100 times with

Table 3: Mobility setting parameters used to perform the simulation.

	RWM	MGM	RPGM
Speed change probability	-	0.4	-
Min. speed	0.5 m/s	0.5 m/s	0.5 m/s
Mean speed	-	1.5 m/s	-
Speed standard deviation	-	0.5	-
Max. speed	2.0 m/s	-	2.0 m/s
Min. pause	60 s	-	-
Max. pause	350 s	350 s	350 s
Pause probability	-	0.2	-
Update distance	-	50 m	-
Turn probability	-	0.5	-
Blocks along x-axis	-	14	-
Blocks along y-axis	-	14	-
Average no. of nodes per group	-	-	$\left\lceil \frac{\text{total no. of nodes}}{3} \right\rceil$
Group change probability	-	-	0.1
Max. distance to group centre	-	-	100 m
Group size standard deviation	-	-	2
Scenario max. x	1000 m	1000 m	1000 m
Scenario max. y	1000 m	1000 m	1000 m

100 different seeds, to prevent random factor influence. The simulated time for each execution was 25200 seconds, i.e., seven hours. This time has been determined as long enough for all the nodes in the network to drain their batteries.

To simulate the execution of a service, the node which hosts the service replica is considered to consume twice as much battery as other nodes, in addition to the natural discharge of the battery and the battery consumed by the network card (the more messages sent, the higher the consumption).

6 Comparative Analysis

A comparative analysis is undertaken within this section that considers each algorithm in terms of message complexity together a number of quality attributes.

6.1 Message Complexity

A message complexity analysis of the selected Bully, Kordafshari, Vasudevan and Consensus election algorithms has been performed. This theoretical analysis helps to reach a better understanding of the behavior of the algorithms in a simplified environment because neither the mobility of the nodes nor message loss is taken into consideration.

In the original version of the Bully and Kordafshari algorithms, the IDs are static and all nodes are know to them. The best case occurs when the node with the highest ID starts the election. The message complexity is $n - 1$.

Introducing the modifications (described in Section 5), the election of both algorithms is based on dynamic scores. Therefore, nodes do not know their neighbors' score, which affects the message complexity and increases it. This is because even if the election is initiated by the highest ranked node, it is not aware of it, and it will send $n - 1$ *election* messages. Since it is the best node, there are no *answer* messages, and the node will proclaim itself as the new coordinator, sending $n - 1$ *coordination* messages. Consequently, the message complexity in the best case will now be given by $2 \cdot (n - 1)$.

The worst case for both algorithms occurs when each node, except that with the highest ID, starts a concurrent election. In this case, the message complexity of the original version of the Bully algorithm is $2n^2 - 1$. However, Kordafshari reduces the number of messages because only the lowest ID node will receive replies to its *election* messages. As a result, the message complexity is $\frac{n^2+5n-2}{2}$. Introducing the modifications, for the Bully algorithm, the following messages will be necessary:

- $n \cdot (n - 1)$ *Election* messages will be sent.
- $\sum_{i=1}^n (n - i)$ *Answer* messages will be sent.
- Finally, the winner of the election process will send $n - 1$ *coordinator* messages.

Therefore, the message complexity will thus be delimited by $\frac{3n^2-n-2}{2}$ messages.

For the Kordafshari algorithm:

- $n \cdot (n - 1)$ *Election* messages will be sent.
- $n - 1$ *Answer* messages are replied only to the lowest ID node.
- The lowest ID node will send a *Grant* message to the elected node.
- The elected node will send $n - 1$ *Coordinator* messages.

The message complexity will be delimited by $n^2 + n - 1$ messages.

In contrast to the Bully and Kordafshari algorithms, the Vasudevan algorithm can operate with an election based on a dynamic score without

any modifications. With this algorithm, the best- and worst-case scenarios are not dependent on who initiates the election but on the topology of the network, since the algorithm that builds a spanning tree to perform the election.

As messages between sibling nodes are unnecessary for the election but inevitable in the growth of the tree, the best case for this algorithm occurs when the network topology is deep and narrow. In this case, $n - 1$ *election*, *ACK* and *leader* messages are sent. Thus, message complexity is given by $3 \cdot (n - 1)$.

The worst-case scenario occurs when the network topology is short and wide, i.e., a mesh topology, because a large number of messages are generated between sibling nodes when building the spanning tree. In this case, the message complexity is given by $2n^2 - 3n + 1$.

The Consensus algorithm is not influenced by neither which node starts the election, nor by the topology of the network. The complexity of the algorithm, both in the worst and best case scenarios, is given as follows:

- $n \cdot (n - 1)$ *Score* messages, since each node broadcasts its score to all nodes except itself.
- $(n - 1)$ *Request* messages, each node, except the best ranked, sends a *request* message to the best ranked.
- $(n - 1)$ *Acceptance* messages, as a reply from the best ranked node to the *request* messages received.

Resulting in a complexity measure of $n^2 + n - 2$.

Table 4 presents a summary of the worst-case and best-case complexity for each of the algorithms. The Vasudevan algorithm presents the worst message complexity and is highly dependent on the nature of network topology.

Bully and Kordafshari algorithms stand out for providing good performance in the best case scenario. In the worst case, which is given by the number of concurrent elections, both present a considerable increase in message complexity. However, this is smaller in the case of the Kordafshari algorithm, due to the improvement introduced over the Bully algorithm to reduce the number of messages.

Consensus and VOELA algorithms present a consistent performance that is not affected by the network topology or concurrent elections. In highly dynamic networks, this is an advantage

in comparison with Bully and Kordafshari, given that the worst case scenario for Bully and Kordafshari will be more frequent. However, in static and reliable networks, the best case scenario will be more frequent for Bully and Kordafshari, and consequently these will present a better performance.

Table 4: Overview of the message complexity of the election algorithms studied.

	Best case	Worst case
Bully	$2 \cdot (n - 1)$	$(3n^2 - n - 2)/2$
Kordafshari	$2 \cdot (n - 1)$	$n^2 + n - 1$
Vasudevan	$3 \cdot (n - 1)$	$2n^2 - 3n + 1$
Consensus	$n^2 + n - 2$	$n^2 + n - 2$
VOELA	$n^2 + (n/2) - 1$	$n^2 + n - 2$

6.2 Empirical Analysis

In the evaluation of the presented proposals, four quality attributes have been measured: (1) **service availability**, (2) **reliability of the election algorithm** in terms of redundant elections, (3) **coordination messages** used in the election process, and (4) **network lifetime**.

Table 5: Network lifetime events and mobility models, and their acronyms.

		Acronym
Events	Time until the First Node Dies	TFND
	Time until Half of the Nodes Die	THND
	Time until the Last Node Dies	TLND
Mobility models	Manhattan Grid Mobility	MGM
	Random Walk Mobility	RWM
	Reference Point Group Mobility	RPGM

In the context of this study, each attributes are defined as follows:

- Service availability is understood to be the time in which a node successfully maintains a client-server connection when there is at least one other reachable node. It is directly related to the speed of the election process and consequently to the election algorithm.
- The reliability of the election algorithm is measured as its capability to avoid undesired redundant server elections in the same group of nodes.

- The number of *coordination* messages used in the election process provides an objective measure of the cost of the election algorithm and is directly implied in the bandwidth and energy consumption. Other measures, such as energy consumption, can differ depending on the technology or evaluation tool.
- Network lifetime is generally defined by the occurrence of three events in the network (Table 5): *Time until the First Node Dies* (TFND), *Time until Half of the Nodes Die* (THND) and *Time until the Last Node Dies* (TLND).

In addition, the algorithms are evaluated with three different mobility models (i.e., Manhattan Grid Mobility, Random Walk Mobility, Reference Point Group Mobility) (Table 5) to compare more holistically algorithm performance.

6.2.1 Service Availability

Mobility is restricted in the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM) model. This results in reduced groups of nodes formed at short distances. The election processes are short and the problems caused by the fading of the connection are consequently reduced. For these reasons, under this model, the availability of service provided by the system with the five LE algorithms is higher than in all other mobility models, which is on average above 90% (Table 6 and Figure 4).

Under the Random Walk Mobility (RWM) model, the Bully and Kordafshari algorithms provide, on average, the best availability results, followed by the proposed new VOELA algorithm, the Vasudevan and Consensus.

In the case of the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) model, the groups of nodes, although more stable, are larger, which implies elections with a greater number of participants. This has a substantial impact on the Vasudevan algorithm with the service availability decreasing to 56.27% for a 30-node network. Other algorithms such as Bully and Consensus, are affected as well, although to a lesser extent. The Kordafshari algorithm is the best performer in terms of service availability under this mobility model, with an average availability of 98.14% and 97.14% in the worst case, followed by VOELA with an average availability of 96.71% and 94.58% in the worst case.

Finally, in Figure 4, the performance in terms of service availability offered by the Vasudevan and Consensus algorithms is considerably lower than that offered by the rest of the algorithms, especially for networks of 20 nodes or more. In the case of the Bully algorithm, its performance in this respect starts to decline noticeably for networks of 25 nodes or more.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	99.65%	99.66%	99.45%	99.74%	99.00%
	Avg	96.70%	97.24%	90.00%	91.53%	94.42%
	Min	89.92%	94.83%	76.61%	76.56%	90.71%
	Std Dev	2.68%	1.50%	7.12%	7.39%	2.44%
RWM	Max	99.56%	99.40%	99.08%	99.66%	98.15%
	Avg	94.77%	95.95%	85.81%	86.84%	92.84%
	Min	79.12%	92.57%	70.71%	65.61%	87.80%
	Std Dev	4.99%	2.09%	8.79%	10.55%	3.00%
RPGM	Max	99.61%	99.57%	96.32%	99.76%	99.26%
	Avg	96.59%	98.14%	89.32%	85.02%	96.71%
	Min	86.56%	97.14%	80.88%	56.27%	94.58%
	Std Dev	3.37%	0.67%	3.63%	13.56%	1.23%

Table 6: Service availability (%) evaluation results obtained under Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models.

6.2.2 Algorithm Reliability

The results provided by the Vasudevan and VOELA algorithms regarding *reliability* are excellent and are not affected by the number of nodes or the mobility models. The percentage of redundant elections on average is always lower than 0.43% in any of the mobility models evaluated (Table 7).

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	13.24%	14.02%	5.94%	0.21%	0.27%
	Avg	8.77%	9.01%	2.72%	0.13%	0.18%
	Min	1.39%	1.49%	0.78%	0.00%	0.05%
	Std Dev	4.21%	4.24%	1.66%	0.06%	0.04%
RWM	Max	18.49%	20.08%	7.30%	0.21%	0.43%
	Avg	12.96%	13.36%	2.72%	0.15%	0.25%
	Min	1.89%	2.22%	1.45%	0.03%	0.06%
	Std Dev	5.50%	5.54%	1.50%	0.04%	0.11%
RPGM	Max	20.68%	23.83%	5.22%	0.61%	0.40%
	Avg	15.40%	16.55%	2.36%	0.16%	0.33%
	Min	2.55%	2.93%	1.02%	0.04%	0.23%
	Std Dev	5.23%	5.82%	1.32%	0.12%	0.05%

Table 7: Evaluation results obtained regarding redundant server elections (%) under Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models.

Fig. 4: Service availability (%) provided by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes.

However, the Bully and Kordafshari algorithms deliver poor *reliability* in terms of the number of redundant elections, mainly due to the number of nodes involved in the election (Figure 5). This can be seen in the results obtained for the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) model (Table 7), where they present their worst results, with an average of 15.40% redundant elections of the total elections performed in the case of the Bully algorithm and 16.55% for the Kordafshari algorithm. For networks of 25 nodes or more in the case of the MGM and RWM models and networks of 20 nodes or more in the case of the RPGM model, it can be observed (Figure 5) that the Bully algorithm generates fewer redundant elections than the Kordafshari algorithm. This is because the Bully algorithm congests the network, which prevent election processes from being completed.

It is worth observing that the Consensus algorithm tends to generate fewer redundant elections the greater the number of nodes involved in the election is (Figure 5). This is due to its mechanism for recovering lost score messages, i.e., the greater the number of nodes in the election, the greater the possibility that these have the correct information and, therefore, a node that has not received it, can recover it. Nevertheless, the results of this algorithm are distant from those provided by the Vasudevan and VOELA algorithms.

6.2.3 Coordination Messages Usage

As can be seen from the data obtained (Table 8) the Kordafshari and VOELA algorithms make the best use of coordination messages. These algorithms need the least number of messages to carry out the election. The Bully algorithm also yields good results, but the number of coordination messages increases considerably for networks larger than 18 nodes (Figure 6). The modifications to the algorithm introduced by Kordafshari do indeed reduce the number of coordination messages with respect to the base of the Bully algorithm.

In the RWM model, the Vasudevan algorithm makes the most intensive use of coordination messages for networks up to 25 nodes. Nevertheless, above 25 nodes, the Bully algorithm uses 3.7 times on average more messages than the Kordafshari algorithm, which is best under this mobility model.

For the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) model (Table 8), on average, the Vasudevan algorithm generates approximately 30.58 times more messages than that of the VOELA algorithm. This intensive use of messages occurs for two main reasons. First, the construction of the spanning tree is especially expensive in mesh networks. Second, when concurrent elections are generated, spanning trees are being built concurrently, and the most recent one will have priority. Therefore, in particular in the case that the interrupted elections are in a final stage of

Fig. 5: Redundant server elections (%) produced by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes.

tree construction, will occur an inefficient use of coordination messages.

In terms of scalability, VOELA and Kordafshari show the best results (Figure 6). It is worth noting that when the number of nodes involved in the election is high, i.e., under the RPGM model, the VOELA and Consensus algorithms perform better in terms of the use of coordination messages. In contrast, under this model, it can be seen how the Vasudevan algorithm starts to collapse the communication network when it is composed of 15-20 nodes, and the Bully algorithm when it is composed of 20-25 nodes. This behavior can also be observed under the RWM model from scenarios composed of 25 nodes for Vasudevan, Bully, and to a lesser extent, for Consensus.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	730,559.00	308,737.00	519,744.00	911,144.00	351,675.00
	Avg	150,063.37	79,623.76	133,955.94	217,979.34	87,924.20
	Min	150.00	184.00	206.00	291.00	173.00
	Std Dev	209,971.17	93,374.56	156,942.13	270,503.17	106,082.64
RWM	Max	2,006,748.00	336,251.00	783,070.00	1,436,328.00	457,042.00
	Avg	397,318.75	106,794.67	217,963.13	399,516.37	128,844.68
	Min	326.00	382.00	450.00	599.00	353.00
	Std Dev	570,303.48	106,646.69	238,702.38	447,988.08	140,416.57
RPGM	Max	4,660,529.00	388,671.00	346,010.00	9,277,770.00	208,752.00
	Avg	683,684.88	85,913.71	115,437.91	1,834,540.31	59,974.17
	Min	210.00	287.00	1747.00	465.00	246.00
	Std Dev	1,220,654.85	109,604.99	104,453.88	2,627,860.82	63,643.44

Table 8: Evaluation results obtained regarding the number of coordination messages produced by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models.

6.2.4 Network lifetime (static evaluation function)

The results of the five algorithms do not show a considerable difference in terms of TFND (Table 9 and Figure 7) for any of the mobility models. Nevertheless, with regard to THND (Figure 8) and TLND (Figure 9) and under the three mobility models, it is possible to identify two groups of algorithms: (1) VOELA, Vasudevan and Consensus; and (2) Bully and Kordafshari. The former group offers an enhanced network lifetime. This is because these algorithms, in contrast to the latter group, generate fewer redundant elections, and therefore, sustain lower battery consumption.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	200.76	202.36	195.89	197.03	201.25
	Avg	190.60	191.82	190.04	188.05	192.62
	Min	183.70	183.98	180.82	181.73	186.03
	Std Dev	3.52	3.85	3.98	3.38	3.56
RWM	Max	201.89	202.73	199.07	199.07	203.79
	Avg	194.46	195.82	195.52	192.87	196.98
	Min	189.04	192.99	191.76	190.03	195.00
	Std Dev	1.61	1.64	1.70	2.51	1.86
RPGM	Max	197.33	197.80	198.71	193.43	199.33
	Avg	191.71	192.35	192.65	187.92	192.93
	Min	158.92	159.84	160.77	154.68	158.02
	Std Dev	8.47	8.42	8.18	8.28	8.38

Table 9: Evaluation results obtained regarding to TFND (minutes) by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models.

Fig. 6: Coordination messages produced by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes.

Fig. 7: Network lifetime (TFND) obtained by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes.

In the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM) model, using the VOELA algorithm, half of the nodes of the network survive on average 22.38 minutes more than using the Kordafshari algorithm (Table 10), and the total network lifetime is extended 32.21 minutes on average (Table 11).

In the case of the Random Walk Mobility (RWM) model, the difference between these algorithms is 40.97 minutes on average for the THND (Table 10) and 53.09 minutes on average for the TLND (Table 11).

A similar difference can be found in the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) model,

in which VOELA extends 36.11 on average on the THND (Table 10) of the network regarding the Kordafshari algorithm and 52.57 minutes on average on the TLND (Table 11).

Regarding the VOELA and Vasudevan algorithms, VOELA generally provides an extended network lifetime of approximately 3-5 minutes on average for the MGM and RWM models and 11.37 minutes for the RPGM model. This variation is because although both generate very few redundant elections, the Vasudevan algorithm makes much more intensive use of coordination messages, which leads to nodes' higher energy consumption.

Fig. 8: Network lifetime (THND) obtained by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes.

Fig. 9: Network lifetime (TLND) obtained by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes.

With regard to the differences presented between the mobility models, the network lifetime is greater in the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) and Random Walk Mobility (RWM) models than in the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM) model. The reason for this is that, in the first two models, the groups of nodes are larger, and therefore, there are more nodes to share the workload of acting as a server.

6.2.5 Network lifetime (self-adaptive evaluation function)

In this section, the self-adaptive evaluation function presented in Section 3.2 is introduced into the system evaluation to increase the lifetime of the network. The monitoring system has been defined so that when the average battery of the group falls below 40%, the weights of the evaluation function initially defined are modified from 0.6 to 0.8 for the battery and from 0.4 to 0.2 for the number of direct connections. In this way, when the battery levels of the nodes in the network start to run low, higher priority is given to those nodes that have

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	230.95	233.62	270.86	269.97	273.99
	Avg	218.02	218.95	237.81	237.36	241.33
	Min	203.96	204.60	201.93	203.21	205.54
	Std Dev	10.17	10.46	26.63	25.88	25.39
RWM	Max	249.75	254.35	321.09	321.07	324.35
	Avg	228.12	228.23	266.42	265.82	269.20
	Min	204.36	205.19	202.58	203.35	207.90
	Std Dev	16.44	17.27	43.91	43.91	42.91
RPGM	Max	251.94	255.84	299.79	289.45	323.38
	Avg	230.58	230.25	259.01	255.68	266.36
	Min	181.01	181.66	183.54	182.29	181.74
	Std Dev	19.93	20.27	35.63	33.04	42.79

Table 10: Evaluation results obtained regarding to THND (minutes) by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	262.73	263.84	305.66	317.79	324.82
	Avg	238.48	239.54	265.24	269.15	271.75
	Min	226.03	228.30	233.92	236.92	239.90
	Std Dev	8.11	8.03	25.05	27.54	28.54
RWM	Max	271.84	275.57	385.65	383.62	386.02
	Avg	243.07	242.02	292.62	293.09	295.11
	Min	220.31	220.64	223.40	226.29	230.29
	Std Dev	18.35	17.80	57.60	56.02	55.99
RPGM	Max	258.92	257.96	355.04	341.02	371.02
	Avg	245.08	243.36	289.59	284.56	295.93
	Min	217.40	219.26	219.93	220.32	224.54
	Std Dev	12.67	11.38	40.10	36.14	44.11

Table 11: Evaluation results obtained regarding to TLND (minutes) by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models.

a higher battery to act as servers of the group. It should be noted that, in the configured scenario, no new nodes are introduced into the network nor do existing nodes recharge their battery during the simulation. The frequency with which nodes report battery levels to their group server is set at 10 minutes. This frequency depends on the specific scenario and the dynamicity of the context value, or values, taken into consideration to trigger the adaptation of the evaluation function. Figure 10 shows the progression of the adaptation of the evaluation function on the nodes of a network composed of 30 nodes. As seen, the speed with which the evaluation function is updated substantially depends on the size of the groups of nodes, being under the RPGM model where the adaptation takes place faster.

To illustrate the interaction of the nodes under this configuration, an example scenario is shown in

Figure 11. It depicts a group of three nodes, where Node 1 acts as the server. Nodes 2 and 3 send to Node 1 their battery levels (b_2 and b_3 in Figure 11) periodically every t_m minutes. Node 1 receives these values and performs the average (\bar{x}) with its own battery level (b_1). When the average battery level of the group falls below 0.4 (i.e., 40%), Node 1 notifies the rest of the nodes to update their evaluation functions.

The results of TFND (Table 12 and Figure 12) compared with the results using a static evaluation function (Table 9) show no noticeable differences. This is because the adaptation in the evaluation function takes place when the average battery of the group falls below 40%; thus at the beginning, when the average battery is above that level, both approaches use the same evaluation function.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	199.77	201.61	197.79	200.41	201.39
	Avg	190.80	192.15	191.90	189.40	194.72
	Min	185.00	186.33	182.46	182.62	185.55
	Std Dev	3.70	3.51	4.20	3.17	2.60
RWM	Max	202.06	202.86	202.14	200.15	208.28
	Avg	195.16	196.08	195.86	193.62	197.84
	Min	190.17	193.52	192.88	189.47	195.12
	Std Dev	2.39	1.86	1.78	2.05	1.90
RPGM	Max	200.09	200.69	201.04	197.89	200.42
	Avg	194.33	194.82	194.74	190.42	195.61
	Min	163.41	162.95	165.30	155.18	162.60
	Std Dev	8.35	8.51	8.06	8.47	8.12

Table 12: Evaluation results obtained regarding to TFND (minutes) by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models using a self-adaptive evaluation function.

However, in the case of THND (Table 13 and Figure 13), a difference can be seen in comparison to the results obtained when using a static evaluation function (Table 10). Specifically, using a dynamic function delays the point at which half of the nodes in the network run out of battery by approximately 8-10 minutes on average, regardless of the evaluation algorithm and the mobility model.

In contrast, no relevant differences can be found in terms of TLND (Table 14 and Figure 14) with respect to the use of a static evaluation function (Table 11). This is because, regardless of which evaluation function is used, all nodes eventually run out of battery. Other factors, such as

Fig. 10: Progression of the adaptation of the evaluation function according to context conditions under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models. The network is composed of a total of 30 nodes and the election algorithm used is VOELA.

Fig. 11: Illustrative example of the iteration of a group of nodes under a self-adaptive evaluation function configuration. Node 1 acts as a server and network monitor. The node evaluation function is updated when the average battery level of the nodes in the group falls below 0.4 (i.e., 40%).

the number of services running and the number of messages sent on the network, determine the TLND.

7 Conclusions and Future Work

The main objective of this research work has been to address the lack of adequate approaches that successfully support the quality attributes of services deployed in advanced mobile systems,

especially when there are *highly dynamic network* topologies operating *under unreliable communication channels*. This work proposes VOELA (voting election algorithm) which scores potential hosts based upon a self-adaptive utility function. VOELA specifically seeks to improve four quality attributes: *service availability*, *reliability* of the election algorithm, use of *coordination messages* and *network lifetime*.

As a result, a comparative analysis is presented across the five LE algorithms that are undertaken: VOELA, developed previously consensus based algorithm, together with three existing reference

Fig. 12: Network lifetime (TFND) obtained by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes using a dynamic evaluation function.

Fig. 13: Network lifetime (THND) obtained by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes using a dynamic evaluation function.

algorithms, Bully, Kordafshari and Vasudevan. The five algorithms have been implemented in Network Simulator 3 (ns-3) and evaluated under three different mobility models, Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM).

Since the original algorithms of Bully and Kordafshari base their election on known IDs, in this work, adaptations have necessarily been made to these algorithms, to base the election on a utility function instead of the IDs of the nodes.

The use of advanced simulation tools allows us to represent the characteristics of a dynamic and

distributed network, and therefore, to undertake the solution considering unreliable communication channels, channel fading and network congestion.

The VOELA algorithm has shown the most balanced results in the four quality attributes analyzed. It should be noted that the Vasudevan algorithm provides a slight increase in reliability, generating on average 0.17% fewer redundant elections under the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) model, but it generates, on average, 30.58 times more messages than the VOELA algorithm. The Kordafshari algorithm provides slightly better service availability; on average, a

Fig. 14: Network lifetime (TLND) obtained by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models in networks from 4 to 30 nodes using a dynamic evaluation function.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	246.56	248.30	295.37	288.69	296.29
	Avg	229.08	225.48	250.54	248.99	254.37
	Min	204.16	204.01	204.24	203.49	213.00
	Std Dev	12.62	11.35	32.65	28.44	32.05
RWM	Max	268.37	274.14	335.39	334.23	338.27
	Avg	237.72	236.45	274.75	272.70	276.34
	Min	205.51	207.37	209.62	204.60	213.85
	Std Dev	18.48	17.01	45.51	44.80	44.47
RPGM	Max	274.68	275.56	329.67	318.66	335.99
	Avg	240.58	238.14	270.36	269.33	275.49
	Min	190.64	187.95	193.81	191.35	194.92
	Std Dev	25.91	21.12	42.48	38.67	44.75

Table 13: Evaluation results obtained regarding to THND (minutes) by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models using a self-adaptive evaluation function.

1.43% increase is made under the Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) model. Nevertheless, the VOELA algorithm provides higher algorithm reliability, generating, on average, 16.22% fewer redundant elections in comparison to the Kordafshari algorithm.

The current proposal assumes that replicas of the service have been previously deployed on the nodes, thus, it is not necessary to transmit the replicas at runtime. Although this approach improves response time and reduces bandwidth consumption, it limits the scenarios where the proposal can be applied to those where the set of services to be used are well-known. This type of scenario is usually related to collaborative work teams, such as rescue teams.

		Bully	Kordaf.	Cons.	Vasu.	VOELA
MGM	Max	263.95	263.93	304.35	319.27	322.26
	Avg	238.60	239.82	264.95	268.93	271.47
	Min	227.25	229.03	235.07	236.09	238.99
	Std Dev	8.24	7.89	24.13	26.92	27.97
RWM	Max	272.24	277.18	386.75	384.95	386.96
	Avg	243.05	242.17	292.59	293.11	295.50
	Min	219.57	221.45	222.80	225.35	230.64
	Std Dev	18.06	17.60	57.15	55.81	55.74
RPGM	Max	258.33	257.45	353.04	340.97	370.77
	Avg	245.38	243.48	289.28	284.54	296.21
	Min	217.84	218.35	221.92	222.32	226.22
	Std Dev	12.59	11.39	39.21	35.63	43.62

Table 14: Evaluation results obtained regarding to TLND (minutes) by the five election algorithms evaluated under the Manhattan Grid Mobility (MGM), Random Walk Mobility (RWM) and Reference Point Group Mobility (RPGM) models using a self-adaptive evaluation function.

Future work will consider the possibility of deploying and transmitting new services in the network at runtime, in order to assess how this approach affects the quality attributes analyzed. Additionally, apply VOELA to larger-scale networks. For this purpose, clustering methods will be studied and integrated within the current proposal. Furthermore, replication synchronization mechanisms will be incorporated, allowing for modification of the shared resources in different partitions of the network. With respect to the self-adaptive evaluation function, in scenarios where new nodes with high battery values may join the network, the average battery value of the group could lead to a misinterpretation of the group status. This could be due to the existence of nodes

with extreme battery values. In this regard, it is proposed to further evaluate the scenarios considered, taking into account those where new nodes may join the network during the execution. Moreover, other approaches can be evaluated, such as not including nodes below a certain battery threshold in the calculation of the average value.

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Data Availability. The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Declarations

On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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